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Research Article

Development and Evaluation of Topical Polyherbal Suspension for Treatment of Inflammation

Osheen Gurung¹, Rashmi Mishra^{2*}, Deepak Shrivastava³, Ankit Sharma⁴, Rajat Pawar⁵, Shivam soni⁶

^{1,2}*Oriental University, Indore.*

³*Shri Bherulal Pharmacy Institute, Indore.*

⁴*Shri Sahaj Institute of Pharmacy, Khargone.*

⁵*Swami Vivekanand College of Pharmacy.*

⁶*Patel College of Pharmacy.*

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ABSTRACT

The current goal is to create a topical Polyherbal suspension that contains guggul to treat anti-inflammatory activities. Several physicochemical characteristics of the developed Polyherbal suspension were assessed. Inflammation is typically created by a combination of the innate immune system and the adaptive immune system. The innate immune system, which includes the activity of different cells like macrophages, mast cells, and dendritic cells, is the body's main line of defense against invasive microorganisms and cancer cells. suspensions are a significant subcategory of pharmaceutical formulations and pose numerous difficulties to formula development personnel. It is of two types flocculated and Non flocculated, Suspension formulated with Guggul (*Commiphora wightii*) is used to treat the Inflammation or has the Anti-inflammatory activity, Guggul is an oleo gum-resin & its composition is made up of resin, gum, volatile oils, moisture, and foreign matter. The formulated suspension was created with a particle size analysis that falls between 15 μ m and 18 μ m. Utilizing a 5.5 PH phosphate buffer and dimethyl sulfoxide solution; the in vitro diffusion release was examined. Utilizing various kinetic models, including zero order, first order, Higuchi plot, Peppas plot, and Hixon plot models, the drug release mechanism of these formulations has been described and it follows the Non Fickian mechanism of transport with release mechanism of both diffusion and relaxation. In vivo studies were also performed using the rat and the inflammation was seen reducing. The formula F4 Compared to other formulations showed the results satisfactory. I discussed the Polyherbal suspension in this paper.

***Corresponding Author:** Rashmi Mishra

Address: Shri Bherulal Pharmacy Institute, Indore.

Email ✉: rajatpawar74@gmail.com

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It also discusses the anti-inflammatory activity and contains benefits, drawbacks, methodology, evaluation, kinetic release, and results.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional system of medicine

Traditional medical systems have long played a significant role in addressing the demands of the world's population in terms of healthcare. Currently, they are doing so, and they will continue to play a significant role in the future. The term "Indian Systems of Medicine" refers to either the medical systems that are believed to have originated in India or the systems that were introduced to India from elsewhere and integrated into Indian culture. Six internationally recognized medical systems are found in India, which is a unique distinction. The following are among them: Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, Yoga, Naturopathy, and Homoeopathy [1].

History of Polyherbal medicine

Mankind has always looked for ways to treat illness and relieve pain. There is evidence of the use of medicinal plants dating back 60,000 years, but more recently, a 5000-year-old clay slab from Sumerian culture was found to confirm the use of medicinal plants for drug preparation. More than 50% of currently available drugs are thought to have some connection to plants. Theae folium, Rhei rhizoma, camphor, podophyllum, jimson weed, and ephedra are just a few of the 365 drugs listed in the Chinese book "Pen Ts'ao" by Emperor Shen Nung [2].

Anti-inflammatory activity

When bacterial, viral, or fungal pathogens enter the body, settle in specific tissues, or circulate in the blood, inflammation frequently results. As a result of conditions like tissue damage, cell death, cancer, ischemia, and degeneration, inflammation may also develop. Inflammation is typically created by a combination of the innate immune system and the adaptive immune system[3].

Process of Inflammation

The four cardinal signs of inflammation are heat, redness, pain, and swelling. The blood vessels' intercellular spaces and increased blood flow are made possible by this, which causes "leaky vessels." Consequently, the injured area can receive fluids, leukocytes, and plasma proteins to help with inflammation. The release of chemical messengers known as chemokine's by mast cells and injured tissue cells is another crucial mechanism. These substances, also known as chemo attractants, produce a chemical gradient that leukocytes travel along in order to get to the inflamed area. These chemicals also have other effects, such as producing heat, enhancing enzyme activity, causing pain, and increasing vascular permeability. Leukotriene's, cytokines, histamine, prostaglandins, and others are a few examples of these chemokine's[4].

Consequences of Inflammation:-Heat at the injury's site, Blotchy skin, Swelling, Tenderness, The signs of chronic inflammation are more subtle than those of acute inflammation, Chest discomfort, Continent pain, Fever, tuberculosis, Mouth ulcers Pain or stiffness in the joints, skin rash, such as psoriasis, Exhaustion[5].

Classification: -Generally speaking, there are two types of inflammation: acute and chronic [6].

Table1: - Classification of Suspension

	Acute	Chronic
Cause	Harmful pathogens or tissue injury.	viruses, persistent foreign bodies, excessive immune reactions, and other pathogens that the body is unable to eliminate.
Initiation	Rapid	Slow
Duration of action	Few days	Months to Years
Result/outcome	Inflammation improves, or an abscess develops or becomes chronic.	Connective tissue scarring, tissue death and tissue thickening.

Inflammation treatment

Usually no treatment or medication is needed for inflammation. For instance, adequate rest, ice application, and proper wound care can all be used to treat the symptoms of acute inflammation. However, depending on your condition and the severity of your chronic inflammation, your doctor may advise one of the following treatments [7] Supplements, NSAIDs, Steroid injections, the swelling and pain brought on by a variety of illnesses and injuries can be lessened with topical anti-inflammatory creams. Common topical anti-inflammatory drugs include the gel form of Voltaren (diclofenac), capsaicin cream, and menthol cream [8].

Suspension

Due to their inherent structural instability, issues with manufacturing, and issues with packaging, suspensions are a significant subcategory of pharmaceutical formulations and pose numerous difficulties to formula development personnel. It depends on the suspension whether it is intended for parenteral use, external application, or oral administration.[9,10] They typically consist of a finely divided solid suspended in a liquid or semi-solid medium, which is the continuous phase. Individual particles in these mixtures typically range in size from 0.5 to 5.0 μ m. nowadays, many suspensions are sold as dry powders that must be "constituted" before use by adding a vehicle in the

prescribed amounts. Such "suspensions" are created primarily for stability-related reasons [11].

Polyherbal Suspension:-Suspension that is formulated with the Polyherbal ingredients is Polyherbal suspension. Suspension formulated with Guggul (*comiphora wightii*) is used to treat the Inflammation or has the Anti-inflammatory activity [12].

2.MATERIAL & METHOD:

Pre- Formulation studies

Pre-formulation investigations are designed to deliver all necessary data (physicochemical characteristics of drug and excipients) which may influence the following:- Formulation Design, Method of manufacturing of the drug product, Evaluations of the resulting product, Packaging of the product[13,14].

Solubility studies of the drug (guggul)

Procedure: - solubility studies of the drug was done using different selected media or solvents, It was done by dissolving the known quantity of drug in a cumulative manner until they remain insoluble in the media[15].The solvents used for dissolving are as follows:

Determination of (λ_{max})

UV Scan range of 200 to 800 nm was selected to determine maximum absorbance of guggul and

alma by using 10 µg/ml solutions the wavelength corresponding to maximum absorbance was found to be 270 nm for guggul and found at 385nm of alma respectively. The λ_{max} values are shown [18].

Determination of Calibration curve Preparation of Standard Solution:

A Stock solution of guggul is prepared by dissolving 100mg pure drug in 10ml DMSO made upto 100 ml with distilled water. From the above solution take 10 ml and diluted to 100ml with distilled water [19,20].

Linearity

Different aliquots of working standard of guggul ranges from 1-10 µg/ml was transferred into series of volumetric flask and total volume was made up to 10 ml with solvent the absorbance was measured at 270 nm against the blank. The linearity is show [21].

MATERIALS AND METHOD: -

Materials: -guggul is taken from the Yucca Enterprises, amla, CMC, Turmericis also from Yucca Enterprises and distilled water from central laboratory.

Table1: -Formulation Development

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Guggul(g)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Alma(g)	1.5	2	2.5	2	2	2	2	1.5	2.5
Carboxymethyl cellulose(g)	3	1.5	2	3	2.5	3	3.5	3.5	3.5
Turmeric(g)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Distilled water(ml)	Q. S								

Methodology (Procedure):

Required quantity of drug and excipients was weighed and passed through the sieve number 100, Now the drug is added to the mortar and pestle and triturate well then add the Amla powder and triturate well, then add the Carboxy methyl cellulose followed by the addition of turmeric powder, Now add the distilled water drop wise and triturate well, finally make up the volume to 100 ml with distilled water.

Evaluation of Suspension

pH: The hydrogen ion concentration's negative logarithm is known as pH. The formula is $\text{pH} = -\log 1/(\text{H}_3\text{O}^+)$ in mathematics. $\text{pH} = -\log(\text{H}_3\text{O}^+)$ because the logarithm of 1 is equal to zero. A pH

metre was used to determine the suspension's pH [22, 23].

Viscosity: -When the solid fraction is higher, the suspension viscosity is higher; when the average particle size is higher, it is lower. For the dependence of the relative viscosity on the solid fraction, many theoretical and semi-empirical closed-form relations have been proposed [24].

Sedimentation method:- To calculate sedimentation, two parameters are studied: Volume of sedimentation, Flocculation level[25].

Rheological method:-It offers details on the habits of Settlers. The viscosity of the suspension is investigated using a Brookfield viscometer. It is fixed with a T-bar spindle and heli path stand. The

resistance the T-bar spindle encounters at different levels is then measured by the viscometer's dial reading as the spindle gently descends into the suspension. This method also identifies the level of the suspension where the structure is stronger as a result of particle agglomeration. The dial reading is plotted against the spindle's number of rotations. The better suspension exhibits a slower rate of dial reading amplification with spindle spins, so the curve is horizontal for an extended period of time [26, 27].

Microbial testing of finished product:-This test is typically carried out to determine whether or not the finished product has any presence of microorganisms.

Two media were used for this test in a common fashion:

1. Tryptone Soya Agar Medium (TSA) for bacterial culture.
2. Sabouraud's Chloramphenicol Agar Medium (SCA) for molds and yeast [28].

Estimating Stability

Finished Product Stability Research

Drug stability is the period of time from the date of manufacture and packaging of the formulation until its chemical or biological activity is not less than a set level of labeled potency and its physical features have not changed noticeably or negatively. The length of the study and the storage conditions are outlined by ICH. Long-term testing for 12 months at 25°C, 2°C, 60% RH, and 5% Rapid testing at 40°C, 2°C, and 75% relative humidity for six months [29,30].

Diffusion Studies:-

In vitro permeation in egg membrane: -

In vitro diffusion studies for all formulations were carried out using Franz diffusion cells. The cell is fabricated with 5mm amber unjacketed and 3ml receptor volume. 10 ml of DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) is made up to 100 ml with 5.5 pH phosphate buffer and this is used as the receptor medium. Egg membrane is used as the dialysis membrane; the membrane is tied to the diffusion cell (donor). Receptor media was added to a donor compartment prior to being mounted on a diffusion cell, A measured quantity of formulation equivalent to 1ml was taken on to the egg membrane and immersed slightly in the receptor medium. [31,32] The entire system was maintained at 37 ± 1°C. An Aliquot of 1 ml was drawn at specific time intervals for 8 hrs. and made up the volume to 10 ml with buffer solution. It was estimated Spectrometrically at 270 nm after each withdrawal the diffusion medium is replaced with an equal volume of fresh medium and % Cumulative release was calculated [33].

In vivo studies:

The average weight of the rat cohort was 180 ± 10 g. The rats were retained in standard laboratory conditions (22 ± 2 °C room temperature and 40–50% relative humidity) with 12 h light and dark cycles, and were fed and watered. Prior to the experiment, the animals were fed pellet food and acclimatized to laboratory conditions for 2 days. Initially plethysmometer was filled with mercury up to the scale reading zero, then rat left paw was dip in the mercury and recorded the readings [34,35]. Now 0.1 mL saline solution of 1% w/v carrageenan of about (0.06ml) was injected to the left paw and left for about 30 mins. then inflammation was observed. A quantity of 5 ml of the test guggul Polyherbal suspension formulation was spread uniformly by massaging repeatedly for 50 times in order to facilitate absorption through the skin of the animal's paw. Leave the animal for

30 min and inflammation was observed for 6hrs (0min, 30min, 1hr, 2hrs, 4hrs, 6hrs) at periodic intervals of time [36].

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION:

Pre-formulation Studies: -Solubility studies were done for drug (guggul)

TABLE 2: - Solubility studies for Drug

Solvents	Solubility	Readings in Percentage
Distilled water	Insoluble	0
Methanol	Sparingly soluble	20
Ethanol	Sparingly soluble	25
Chloroform	Sparingly soluble	30
Acetone	Sparingly soluble	50
Phosphate buffer	Sparingly soluble	60
Dimethyl Sulfoxide	Soluble	99

From the above table the active ingredient is soluble in the DMSO

Determination of Wavelength:

The wave length was found to be 270nm for the active ingredient.

FTIR Studies

FIG 3: - FTIR Studies of Guggul

Fig 4: - FTIR Studies of F4 Formulation

Table 3: -Standard Calibration Curve

S. No	Concentration	Absorbance
1	0.2	0.101±0.03
2	0.4	0.174±0.03
3	0.6	0.277±0.03
4	0.8	0.390±0.03
5	1.0	0.552±0.03

Each value represents mean values of \pm s.d. (n=3)

Fig 5: -calibration curve of guggul

Evaluations:

Table 5: -

Formulations	Re-Dispensability	PH	Nature	Colour	Odour	Particle Size
F1	Inversion	4.2	Suspension	Yellow	Characteristic	15 μ m
F2	Inversion	4.25	Suspension	Yellow	Characteristic	14 μ m
F3	Inversion	5	Suspension	Yellow	Characteristic	14 μ m
F4	Inversion	5	Suspension	Yellow	Characteristic	14.5 μ m
F5	Inversion	5.1	Suspension	Yellow	Characteristic	13.5 μ m
F6	Inversion	5.2	Suspension	Yellow	Characteristic	13 μ m
F7	No Inversion	5.25	Cream	Yellow	Characteristic	16 μ m

F8	No Inversion	5.5	Cream	Yellow	Characteristic	16.8µm
F9	No Inversion	5.5	Cream	Yellow	Characteristic	18µm

From the above table the redispersibility, Nature studies F1to F6 shows inversion and suspension whereas F7 to F9 shows no inversion and as cream, F4 shows optimized PH, and particle size 14.5µm, all the formulations show yellow colour and characteristic odor.

Table 6: -Viscosity: -viscosity of sample was determined at room temperature by using Brookfield viscometer at 50 RPM.

Formulations (CP)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Spindle (61)	48.5	49.2	51.2	53.2	46.2	40.0	38.2	30.1	26.2
Spindle (62)	50.2	50.9	54.6	54.8	47.3	38.2	36.4	28.9	24.1
Spindle (63)	51.8	51.9	55.6	56.6	48.4	38.1	32.1	26.4	20.2
Average value (CP)	50.1	50.6	53.8	54.8	47.3	38.7	35.5	28.4	23.5

From the above table F4 showed the best result with 54.8cp.

Table 7: - Sedimentation Volume

Formulation	5days	10days	15 days	20 days	25days	30days
F1	1.03	0.98	0.96	0.9	0.89	0.85
F2	1.02	0.94	0.9	0.85	0.82	0.79
F3	1.01	0.93	0.86	0.81	0.78	0.75
F4	1.02	0.97	0.95	0.93	0.91	0.88
F5	1.01	0.92	0.84	0.8	0.77	0.72
F6	0.97	0.92	0.89	0.83	0.76	0.7

Fig 6: - Representing Sedimentation Volume

Microbial Testing

Table: - Microbial Testing of Finished Product

S. No	Observation	Accelerated condition for 3 months	Real time condition for 3 months	Refrigeration condition for 3 months
1	Before Incubation	Nil	Nil	Nil
	a) Total Bacterial Count			
	b) Total fungal Count	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	After Incubation	16 CFU/ml	Nil	Nil
	a) Total Bacterial Count			
	b) Total Fungal Count	Nil	Nil	Nil

Various storage setups were used to keep the optimal F4 formulation. Checks for microbiological contamination were made on the product during storage. 16 bacterial colonies were discovered to have generated under expedited settings for this formulation (F4), however they were discovered to be within acceptable bounds.

Both in the accelerated and real-time situations, there were no countable fungal colonies visible.

Estimating stability

Finished product stability research

Table: Stability Studies of Formulated Polyherbal Suspension (Formulation F4)

S. NO	Evaluation Test	Accelerated condition for 3 months	Real time condition for 3 months
1	Colour	No change	No change
2	pH	No change	No change
3	Viscosity	54.8cps	53.9cp
4	Sedimentation volume	0.95	0.95

Table: Stability studies of formulated Polyherbal Suspension under Refrigeration condition (Formulation F4)

S.NO	Evaluation Test	Refrigeration condition for 3 months

1	Colour	No change
2	pH	No change
3	Viscosity	54.8cps
4	Sedimentation volume	0.95

In Vitro Diffusion Studies:

Time(min)	Cumulative % Drug Release					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6

0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5	39.80±0.06	32.52±0.05	31.57±0.012	40.43±0.09	47.57±0.09	32.39±0.07
10	55.32±0.05	47.17±0.09	43.03±0.09	63.82±0.010	69.20±0.07	59.72±0.010
15	71.40±0.007	54.53±0.005	52.17±0.006	77.58±0.005	79.39±0.012	75.72±0.012
20	84.62±0.008	68.82±0.007	64.72±0.005	87.95±0.006	89.33±0.014	84.74±0.024
25	87.22±0.012	72.24±0.014	73.32±0.011	94.45±0.012	96.52±0.017	90.42±0.126
30	91.30±0.014	86.95±0.012	85.09±0.001	98.99±0.001	102.06±0.124	94.06±0.128

Each value represents mean values of \pm s.d. (n=3) **Zero order drug release**

Fig 10: - Graph Of Zero Order

From the above table F4 is the best formulation for the zero order First order drug release

Fig 11: - Graph of for First Order

From the above table F4 is the best formulation for **Higuchi Plot Time** the first order

Fig 12: - Graph of Higuchi Plot Time

From the above table F4 is the best formulation for **Korsmeyer Peppas Plot** the Higuchi plot time

Fig 13: - Graph of Korsmeyer Peppas Plot Time

From the above table F4 is the best formulation for **Hixon Crowell Plot** the Korsmeyer plot time

Fig 14: - Graph Of Hixon Crowell Plot Time

From the above table F4 is the best formulation for the Hixon plot time.

Slope and r2 Values Table 22: -

Formulation	zero order		Frist order		Higuchi Plot		Korsmeyer -Peppas Plot		Hixon plot	
	R2	Slope	R2	Slope	R2	Slope	R2	Slope	R2	Slope
F1	0.9506	3.2462	0.2642	0.0843	0.4897	2.4969	0.9315	1.44	-2.048	1.3692
F2	0.8842	3.4374	0.194	0.0857	0.8682	2.2909	0.9141	1.4698	-1.708	1.178
F3	0.8892	3.5209	0.1737	0.0862	0.8744	2.0509	0.906	1.4797	-1.589	1.0945
F4	0.9506	3.6923	0.1596	0.0872	0.7108	2.3538	0.9012	1.4973	-1.328	0.9231
F5	0.8438	3.644	0.116	0.087	0.8155	2.2524	0.8862	1.4977	-1.406	0.9714
F6	0.8413	3.5516	0.1076	0.0865	0.8964	1.9614	0.8823	1.4894	-1.555	1.0637

In vivo studies Table 23: -

Time (Min)	Level (ML)
0	0.4
30	1.5
60	1.4
120	1
240	0.8
480	0.5

From the above table it is seen that the level of Inflammation decreases as the duration of time increases.

Fig: -Plethysmometer

Fig: - Rat Paw Before Inflammation

Fig: - Rat Paw After Inflammation

Fig: -Invivo Studies On Rat

Summary: -

The aim of the current study is to develop and evaluate the topical Polyherbal suspension using

guggul as the active pharmaceutical ingredient. As per the preliminary research, it is shown that it aid in the treatment of some anti- inflammatory conditions like arthritis, psoriasis, eczema, and a variety of skin diseases like acne. Additionally, it has been utilized to treat hypothyroidism, encourage weight loss, and regulate blood sugar and cholesterol levels. But Now our study only says or discusses about the anti-inflammatory activity using various excipients which includes Amla, Carboxy methyl cellulose and Turmeric we used mostly all the Polyherbal ingredients so there will be the minimal side effects, and all these materials are available at low cost in the market. from the study it is shown that the formulated Polyherbal suspension reduces the inflammation. *Guggul* Polyherbal suspension was prepared by using guggul as drug and Amla, CMC, Turmeric as excipients. The physicochemical characteristics of the formulations were studied the particle size range of the prepared formulation lies from 15 μ m to 18 μ m.Redispersibility studies were performed were F1 to F6 shows inversion and F7 to F9 doesn't show inversion. Viscosity studies were performed by using three spindles (61,62,63) and F4 formulation showed the best result of 54.8%. Sedimentation parameters are also performed from 5 days to 30 days were F4 formulation showed the best result. The microbial studies were performed for F4 formulation and 16 bacterial colonies were observed *Invitro* diffusion studies were studied using the egg membrane as a diffusive membrane were F4 formulation showed the best result of 97.99%.*Invivo* studies were performed using the rat and the result was found to be satisfactory as the inflammation is seen reducing. Finally F4 formulation is considered to be the best formulation among all the studies as it showed the optimum results.

CONCLUSION: -

Guggul Polyherbal suspension for anti-inflammatory activity was prepared by using different excipients (Amla, Carboxy methyl cellulose and Turmeric) it was concluded that the formulation F4 showed the satisfactory results compared to other formulations of F1,F2,F3,F5,F6,F7,F8,F9.

REFERENCES

1. B. ravishankar and vj shukla, indian systems of medicine: A brief profile, african journal of traditional, complementary and alternative medicine: Ajtcam, 2007 feb 16.
2. M. M. Pandey, subha rastogi, and a. K. S. Rawat, indian traditional ayurvedic system of medicine and nutritional supplementation, 23 jun 2013.
3. Yu shi a, chao zhang a, xiaodong li b, traditional medicine in india, journal of traditional chinese medical sciences, 1, november 2021.
4. Sumner j. The natural history of medicinal plants, london: Timber press; 2000. Pp. 16.
5. Yarnell nd, abascal jd. Dilemmas of traditional botanical research. Polyherbal gram 2002; 55:4654. fabricant ds, farnsworth nr. The value of plants used in traditional medicine for drug discovery. *environ. Health perspect* 2001; 109.
6. Wiart c. Ethnopharmacology of medicinal plants. New jersey: Humana press; 2006. Pp. 1–50.
7. Katic r. The chilandar medical codex n. 517. In: Milicevic v, editor. Beograd: National library from srbija; 1980. Pp. 9–80.
8. Dwivedi g, dwivedi sh. History of medicine. National informatics center. Retrieved 2008; 8-10.
9. Vulgaris TH. PDR for Polyherbal medicine. Montvale NJ, london: Medical economics company; 2004. Pp. 1184.
10. Jacquart d. Islamic pharmacology in the middle ages: Theories and substances. *Eur rev* 2008; 16(2):219
11. Millie g. Reading medicine in the codex de la cruz badiano. *j hist ideas* 2008; 69(2):169-192.
12. Swerdlow jl. Modern science embraces medicinal plants. *Nature's medicine: Plants that heal*. Washington, dc: National geographic society; 2000. Pp. 110–57.
13. Kovacevic n. Fundamentals of pharmacognosy. Beograd: Personal edition; 2000. Pp. 170–10
14. Ahmad nassar, and abed n. Azab, norbert latruffe, anti-inflammatory activity of natural products, *molecules*. 2016 oct; 21(10): 1321.
15. Tk mohamed saleem, ak azeem, c dilip, c sankar, nv prasanth, and r duraisamy, anti-inflammatory activity of the leaf extracts of *gendarussa vulgaris nees*, *asian pacific journal of tropical biomedicine*, 2011 apr; 1(2): 147–149.
16. Farhat yasmeen sadiq basha , rajeshkumar, ss raj, uses of medicinal plants for anti-inflammatory activity - a review, *European journal of molecular & clinical medicine* , volume 07, issue 01, 2020.
17. Hindu rao, austin ulrich, anti-inflammatory creams for pain: What you need to know, june 28, 2022.
18. Lea and febiger, howard c., Introduction of pharmaceutical dosage forms, 1981, 139- 166.
19. Habib mj, mesue r. Development of controlled release formulations of ketoprofen for oral use. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 1995; 21(12):1463- 1472.
20. Aulton me, taylor k, pharmaceuticals: The design and manufacture of medicines. Elsevier health sciences; 2013.
21. Krishna r, yu l, biopharmaceuticals applications in drug development. Springer science & business media; 2007.

22. Habib mj, mesue r. Development of controlled release formulations of ketoprofen for oral use. *Drug devind pharm.* 1995;21(12):1463-72. tykhonov oi, yarynykh th. *Pharmacy technology of drugs.* Nova knyha: Vinnytsia ukraine. 2016;536.
23. Liquid medicinal forms. On the materials of the foreign press. *Pharm branch.* 2017;3:26-37.
26. kawashima y, iwamoto t, niwa t, takeuchi h, itoh y. Preparation and characterization of a new controlled release ibuprofen suspension for improving suspendability. *Int j pharm.* 1991;75(1):25-36.
24. Arora k, vats v, verma pk, a review on pharmaceutical suspension and its advancement, 25 oct 2022.
25. Katherine marengo ldn, r.d., nutrition — by kaitlyn berkheiser , guggul: Benefits, dosage, side effects, on august 12, 2020.
26. M. Z. Siddiqui, m. Thomas 1 and n. Prasad, physicochemical characterization and antioxidant activity of essential oils of guggul (*commiphora wightii*) collected from madhya pradesh, *indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 18 april 2013.
27. Catherine ulbricht a, ethan basch b, philippe szapary c, paul hammerness d, serguei axentsev e, heather boon f, david kroll g, levi garraway d, mamta vora h, jen woods h, natural standard research collaboration, guggul for hyperlipidemia: A review by the natural standard research collaboration, *complementary therapies in medicine*, volume 13, issue 4, december 2005, pages 279-290
28. Diksha gupta, dr. Deepak soni, dr. Ashish ranjan, guggul, 29 aug 2022.
32. francesco donato; elena raffetti; giuseppe toninelli; andrea festa; carmelo scarcella;
29. Maurizio castellano; guggulu and triphala for the treatment of hypercholesterolaemia: A placebo-controlled, double-blind, randomised trial, november 26, 2020.
30. Abbas fa, al-massarany sm, khan s, al-howiriny ta, mosa js, abourashed ea, phytochemical and biological studies on saudi *commiphora opobalsamum* l. *Nat. Prod. Res.* 21: 383-391, (2007).
31. Hammer ka, carson cf, riley tv, antimicrobial activity of essential oils and other plant extracts. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 86:985-990, (1999).
32. Romero cd, chopin sf, buck g, martinez e, garcia m, bixby l. antibacterial properties of common Polyherbal remedies of the southwest, *j99*:253-257, (2005).
33. Bhattacharya, a.; chatterjee, a.; ghosal, s.; bhattacharya, s. K. (1999). "Antioxidant activity of active tannoid principles of *emblica officinalis* (amla)". *Indian journal of experimental biology.* 37 (7): 676–680.

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